

Using Deep Learning and Low-Frequency Fourier Analysis to Predict Parameters of Coupled Non-Linear Oscillators for the Generation of Complex Rhythms

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes a method for generating rhythmic structures using non-linear coupled oscillators and a machine learning model. The method is based on the Kuramoto model, a mathematical model used to describe the collective behavior of a system of oscillators, and a multi-layer perceptron neural network. The goal of this approach is not to exactly reproduce input rhythms, but rather to develop a form of interaction with chaotic processes for experimental musical practice. The system consists of three components: the generative component producing rhythms, a method for the analysis of rhythmic structures, and a machine learning model that learns the relationships between the parameters of the rhythm generation and the analysis. The Kuramoto model was chosen due to its potential to mediate between periodicity and chaos, creating aesthetically rich and fruitful material for the author's musical practice. The other components serve to explore this model in new ways and to couple it to external rhythmic musical signals.

1. INTRODUCTION

This paper presents a method to generate rhythmic structures with non-linear coupled oscillators whose parameters are predicted by a machine learning model. The system as a whole takes audio input and synthesizes similar rhythmic structures. In general, the approach presented in this paper is similar to automatic synthesis parameter estimation with machine learning [1, 2], where an input sound is to be matched. After training a neural network to associate spectral analysis data with parameter settings, this matching is produced by predicting parameters for a sound synthesis process that reproduce the input target sound as closely as possible. However, the method described here is different in several ways. First, it is focused on low-frequency (rhythmic) dynamics and amplitude envelopes. Second, the generative element is not an established synthesis method, but a network of three coupled non-linear

oscillators, which produces such low-frequency signals. Third, the aim of this approach is principally explorative and artistic in nature. The method thus applies approaches from the field of sound synthesis to the generation (and analysis) of lower-frequency musical structures, such as rhythm.

The matching process is based on a low-frequency spectral analysis described below and a machine learning model, using a neural network. Essentially, the system consists of three components:¹

1. The generative component producing rhythmic structures (sound synthesis, implemented in SuperCollider)
2. A method for the analysis of rhythmic structures based on audio data (also implemented in SuperCollider)
3. A machine learning model that learns the relations between the parameters of the rhythm generation and the analysis (implemented in Python)

The aim of the method presented is to develop a low-frequency, dynamic form of coupling of musical processes for experimental musical practice. This means that the exact reproduction of input rhythms is not the goal, but rather the explorative development of a form of interaction with chaotic processes. The user of the system can explore the dynamics of the coupled non-linear oscillators by means of audio input. This opens up possibilities for ensemble playing, composition and coupling with other generative processes. Moreover, the method described in this paper may be applied to other generative components.

The project seeks to help discover novel ways of composing and performing with coupled non-linear oscillators by opening up a way to interact with such systems not only via manipulating the different parametrical dimensions separately but via audio input and via a prior mapping of the parametric space of such a generative model. The collection and curation of the training data set, by way of shaping and limiting the parametric space to be mapped, is already seen as part of the compositional creation. In this way, it seeks to extend the idea of entrainment inherent to the generative systems to a meta-control level.

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¹The SuperCollider components can be found at <https://github.com/lucdobereiner/KuraLFNN> and the Python component can be found at <https://github.com/lucdobereiner/MLOsc>

2. THE GENERATIVE COMPONENT: NON-LINEAR COUPLED OSCILLATORS

The central generative component in the described system consists of three circularly connected non-linear oscillators as depicted in fig. 1.

Figure 1. Network of three interacting oscillators

Coupled non-linear oscillators are dynamical systems composed of interacting elements that exhibit many interesting properties for music and sound-based artistic practices. Coupled non-linear oscillators, such as the Kuramoto model, can generate complex rhythms, especially if the coupling topology involves feedback. Subtle changes in coupling strength and fundamental frequencies let such systems exhibit chaotic as well as interesting quasi-periodic behavior. They can exhibit synchronizing behavior with regard to other oscillators (and possibly external input) and unfold chaotic dynamics. Their capacity to generate rhythms is particularly interesting in this context, because they can link together independently interacting processes and thus exhibit collective, self-organizing behavior. In scientific and engineering fields, systems such as the Kuramoto model, which is used here, are employed, for example, to model physical and neurobiological processes and, famously, to model the synchronization of flashing patterns of fireflies [3]. Coupled synchronizing oscillators have also been used successfully for sound synthesis and rhythm generation [4, 5]. The project presented in this paper seeks to extend previous work done on using Kuramoto models for the generation of rhythmic structures [6] and introduces machine learning to further explore its capacities.

The system presented is based on the Kuramoto model. The Kuramoto model is a mathematical model used to describe the collective behavior of a system of oscillators. It was first proposed by Yoshiki Kuramoto in 1975 [7] and has since become one of the most widely used models for the study of synchronization. The model consists of a set of oscillators with different fundamental frequencies that are connected by interactions, which can be either attractive or repulsive. Equation (1) describes the model. K is the coupling strength, N is the number of connected oscillators, ϕ is the phase and ω is the fundamental frequency, independent of synchronization.

$$\dot{\phi}_i = \omega_i + \frac{K}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N \sin(\phi_j - \phi_i) \quad (1)$$

The Kuramoto model is suitable for creating complex networks of oscillators. The design of network topographies can have an enormous influence on the emerging behavioral possibilities and thus also has striking artistic po-

tential. In the system described here only three coupled oscillators are used, each having an independent coupling strength parameter (see equation 2). The number of oscillators is intentionally small for this first investigation, so that the number of parameters can be kept small and the interaction of the system components remains comprehensible.

Configurations of negative and positive coupling values, as well as the use of large coupling values, create engaging, complex dynamics ranging from periodic synchronized structures to chaotic states. Finally, we added an independent low-frequency noise (r). Low noise coupling values hardly affect the system, but higher values can lead to desynchronization or slow down synchronization processes, divert and reinitiate them, creating another musically productive way of interacting with the model.

$$\dot{\phi}_i = \omega_i + \frac{K_i}{3} \sum_{j=1}^3 \sin(\phi_j - \phi_i + r) \quad (2)$$

The motivation for using the Kuramoto model was not primarily its ability to produce coherent, uniform patterns, but rather its potential to mediate between periodicity and chaos. In particular, uneven coupling strengths and disturbance due to noise create chaotic dynamics [8], with continuous changes in parameters creating musical material that is aesthetically rich and fruitful for the author's musical practice. Due to the possibility of navigating phase transitions, synchronization and desynchronization and rendering these sonically experienceable, this generative model is suitable as a versatile core of the described system. The other components of the system (analysis and prediction with machine learning) essentially serve to explore this model in new ways and to couple it to external rhythmic musical signals.

The generative model, as it is implemented in SuperCollider, has the following seven parameters:

- Fundamental frequency of oscillator 1 (ω_1)
- Fundamental frequency of oscillator 2 (ω_2)
- Fundamental frequency of oscillator 3 (ω_3)
- Coupling strength influencing oscillator 1 (K_1)
- Coupling strength influencing oscillator 2 (K_1)
- Coupling strength influencing oscillator 3 (K_1)
- Strength of low-frequency noise influencing all three oscillators (r)

Whenever an oscillator completes a period (2π), a 90ms sine burst is triggered. The sine wave of each of the three oscillators in the network has a slightly different frequency. The three oscillators are mixed and used as input to the analysis component.

3. THE ANALYSIS COMPONENT: RHYTHM SPECTRUM

The rhythmic structures generated by the system described above are analyzed with a low-frequency Fourier analysis to obtain a *rhythm spectrum*. In doing so, this project relies heavily on the spectral speech rhythm analysis method of Tilsen and Johnson [9]. In contrast to common methods in speech analysis, which use interval durations to describe the temporal patterns of speech, Tilsen and Johnson focus on acoustic features and in particular on the amplitude envelope.

Similar to the method described by Tilsen and Johnson, the system described here derives a frequency-domain representation from the time-domain amplitude envelope. In this adaptation, implemented in SuperCollider and making use of its capacity to perform FFT on control rate data, we collect 4096 downsampled control rate values of the amplitude envelope (RMS) of the signal to be analyzed. With a block size of 64 samples and a sample rate of 48000 Hz the control rate is 750 Hz. One frame to be analyzed (4096 samples) represents about 5.46 seconds. Prior to applying the Fourier transform (with a Hanning window), the amplitude envelope is normalized to unit variance. The resulting magnitude spectrum now shows the strength of rhythmic periodicity. The analysis component can be summarized in the following way:

Amplitude Envelope → **Downsampled Envelope** → **FFT** → **First 200 Magnitudes** → **Rhythm Spectrum**

Figure 2. Analysis component

However, since we are only interested in low frequencies, we are only using the first 200 bins. In other words, the rhythm spectrum consists of the magnitudes of the first 200 bins of the frequency domain representation of the downsampled amplitude envelope of the input signal.

Fig. 3 shows the rhythm spectrum of a 25 frames (5.46 seconds each) of Iannis Xenakis composition *Psappha* and fig. 4 shows the rhythm spectrum of an excerpt of Farben’s 2002 minimal house track *Live At The Sahara Tahoe, 1973*, while fig. 5 shows the rhythm spectrum of an excerpt of Arnold Schönberg’s *Zwei Klavierstücke, Op. 33*. Strong periodicities are clearly detectable in fig. 4, but it is also striking how overall spectral features, such as the spectral envelope and its peakiness are rhythmically meaningful properties in this form of representation.

4. THE MACHINE LEARNING COMPONENT

The machine learning component functions as a way of linking the analysis with the parameter space of the generative component. Its input is analysis data (a rhythm spectrum) and its output is a parameter setting for the generative component.

It consists of a feed-forward multilayer perceptron model [10]. The dataset is made up of the set of rhythm spectrums (each being a vector of 200 elements) as input data and the set of the respective seven parameter values as tar-

Figure 3. Rhythm spectrum of 25 frames (5.46 seconds each) of Iannis Xenakis’ composition *Psappha*.

Figure 4. Rhythm spectrum of 25 frames (5.46 seconds each) of Farben’s 2002 minimal house track *Live At The Sahara Tahoe, 1973*.

get data. The model has four hidden layers, an input size of 200 (due to the dimensions of the rhythm magnitude spectrum) and an output size of 7 (the number of parameters of the generative model, see above). Each hidden layer has 200 neurons. It is a supervised learning regression task, using the average mean squared error between the predicted seven parameter values and the actual parameter values in the training data set as the loss function and the adam optimizer. It uses a batch size of 32. The model was trained for 1000 epochs. Fig. 6 shows the evolution of the loss. These hyperparameters were established experimentally. The model was implemented in Python using TensorFlow and communicates with SuperCollider using OSC.

The dataset consists of 500 parameter settings and their respective rhythm spectrums. These parameter settings were chosen randomly, but within particular limits that were established through musical experiments. Different random distributions for the coupling values, including Gaussian and exponential distributions were used, as well as only positive or positive and negative coupling values. Different

Figure 5. Rhythm spectrum of 25 frames (5.46 seconds each) of Arnold Schönberg’s *Zwei Klavierstücke, Op. 33*.

Figure 6. The evolution of the loss

basic frequency values of the Kuramoto oscillators were used as well. The different limits and random distributions define particular zones that appear musically interesting to the author. Since the rhythm spectrum can represent periodicities of up to 5.46 seconds, each parameter setting ran for 6 seconds. Structures and developments that last longer than 5.46 seconds, which the Kuramoto oscillator network is capable of producing cannot be captured. Between each data sample, the system was given 2 seconds to converge to the next parameter setting.

At this stage, we have not introduced any form of regularization or other techniques to prevent overfitting. In contrast, when deliberately designing the training set, a certain degree of overfitting may be musically desirable.

5. RESULTS

The first important results of the project are the three individual system components themselves. The exploration of non-linear oscillator networks for rhythm generation is an engaging area for future research and the model developed here is small while capable to produce a rich variety

of complex (and less complex) rhythmic structures. Furthermore, the spectral representation of rhythms and its implementation is an important contribution and result of this project. Third, the application of machine learning to chaotic systems is a highly rewarding musical research area to which this project contributes.

A limitation that must be dealt with in the future arises from the window size of the input buffer. This duration often becomes noticeable through periodicities in the output. Another problem is dealing with silence and continuous, non-pulsating amplitude envelopes. A musically important material is the collection of training data. In addition to the described regular sampling of the parameter space, more curated, smaller sets of parameter settings were also tried. Thus, more musically specific behaviors can be developed, as the possibility space of the generative system is thus much more compositionally pre-designed.

Since the aim of this project is not to reproduce the target dynamics but to exploratively enable aesthetically engaging forms of coupling of the generative system with external input, the results need to be evaluated aesthetically and a purely data centered form of evaluation would fall short. The system has been tested with musical input including recordings of rhythmically complex music, as well as rhythmically more repetitive music and more continuously evolving music. The repository <https://github.com/lucdoebereiner/KuraLFNN> contains three short sound examples, with the Kuramoto network on the left channel and the input to be matched on the right channel. Every 5.46 seconds a new parameter setting is generated.

5.1 Farben, *Live At The Sahara Tahoe, 1973*

The first example is taken from Farben’s 2002 minimal house release *Textstar+*. The generated rhythms match the overall tempo and regularity of the input. Some parameter settings emphasize quarter notes while others seem to focus on lower level rhythmic structures. This example shows how sensitive the overall system is to small changes in the rhythm spectrum, as input passages with little rhythmic changes can create a vast range of different rhythms generated by the generative component.

5.2 Iannis Xenakis, *Psappha*

A second example is Iannis Xenakis’ composition *Psappha* for solo percussion. The generated output is relatively sparse and matches the overall density and regularity of the input. Especially noticeable is how it reproduces the mixture of slow regular rhythms and short groups of faster rhythms separated by longer rests.

5.3 Arnold Schönberg, *Zwei Klavierstücke, Op. 33*

The third example is an excerpt of Schönberg’s composition *Zwei Klavierstücke, Op. 33* for solo piano. This example is characterized by a much greater degree of rhythmic irregularity and changes in density. The generated rhythms match this variety in density and what is especially notice-

able are the quasi-periodic patterns that are more complex than the rhythms generated in the other two examples.

6. FUTURE WORK

We have experimented with extending the approach of Tilsen and Johnson by applying a mel frequency scaled filterbank as well as a logarithmically scaled filter bank on the power spectrum, with 40 bands and 16 bands respectively. Different types of scaling will be explored in the future.

The approach described in this paper is only a first step and has already yielded artistically engaging results. A large number of possible extensions and research questions open up, both technical and artistic. For example, it would be interesting to apply spectral descriptors and features, which are mostly used to describe timbres, to the rhythm spectra, such as centroid, kurtosis, spread, and roll off. In addition, the representation of the rhythmic spectrum, directly as magnitude spectrum or scaled in mel bands should be further investigated and the applicability of scaled filter banks in low-frequency ranges should be reconsidered. Musically, the described system also lends itself to the generation of low-frequency structures in general, here also less "rhythmic" but slow envelope progressions should be considered. Great development potential also lies in the generative system, which was intentionally reduced in this model. Larger oscillator networks would lend themselves here. Most importantly, the method developed here must be evaluated and exhausted in musical and compositional practice.

7. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, this paper outlines an approach to generating complex rhythms with non-linear coupled oscillators using deep learning and low-frequency Fourier analysis. The system presented consists of three Kuramoto models connected in a circular topology and a deep learning model that predicts parameters for the rhythm generation based on low-frequency spectral analysis. The method provides a way of adapting the non-linear oscillators to the rhythmic structures of incoming audio streams and offers a very specific form of interaction with chaotic processes for musical and sound-based artistic practices. The use of the Kuramoto model, known for its capacity to exhibit complex dynamics ranging from periodic synchronization to chaos, was motivated by its potential to mediate between periodicity and chaos.

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